

The *Bargit*, A Uniquetraditional Art Skill in Śankari Teaching System

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The system of Śankarî teaching may be considered to start from the event of Cihnayâtrâ, the first drama introduced by Śankaradeva in 1468 A.D. It was an innovative initiative of Śankaradeva to adopt mass communication as the media of teaching. The system of Śankarî teaching involves literatures, dramas, songs, dances and musical instruments as the instruments of Śankarî teaching. It was evolved in thâna, satra and nâmgâra, and later it reached mass people following Śankarî ideology. The Śankarî teaching was initiated by Śankaradeva and Mâdhavadeva, and later enriched and propagated by their disciples. Amongst various instruments of Śankarî teachings, *bargît* is a fine traditional art form consisting skills of singing, playing instruments, maintaining beats and rhythm of instrument (khola) and cymbal (tâla), classical musical knowledge of raga, notation, voice modulation and so on. Apart from technical expertise, it also involves grasping of its literary meaning and lyrical, aesthetic beauty. Skill development is an important objective of education in the area of psychomotor domain of personality development. The various forms of performing art, games, sports and other vocations encompass the objective of skill development in modern education. *Bargît* plays a very important role in Śankarî teaching system to teach the people *bhakti* and devotion to God through the practice of fine art and skill development.

Bargîts are very closely related to the Sattriya dance form. Various Sattriya dance forms are performed on the beats of Khol along with singing of *bargît*. Since the Sattriya dance form has been recognized as a Classical dance form of India, *bargît* is also claimed to be classical music. Being a unique traditional music, *bargîts* have several classical elements with its ragas and rythms. Preservation and development in its real spirit is most important while *bargîts* are used as a performing art as well as using as a means of Śankarî teaching.

The objective of this work is to critically analyze the place of *bargîts* in the system of Śankarî teaching, to identify the elements of skills in *bargîts*, to see the relevance of *bargîts* as a domain of skill development and its preservation as an art form.

Keywords: Śankarîteaching, education, psychomotor skill, *bargît*, mass communication, communication process, art, science.